

CLINICAL-MORPHOLOGICAL STATUS OF FETOPLACENTAL COMPLEX IN PREGNANT PATIENTS WITH COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the clinical-morphological status of the fetoplacental complex in pregnant patients with covid-19. Since the beginning of the pandemic, few papers describe the placenta's morphological and morphometrical features in SARS-CoV-2-positive pregnant women. Alterations, such as low placental weight, accelerated villous maturation, decidual vasculopathy, infarcts, thrombosis of fetal placental vessels, and chronic histiocytic intervillitis (CHI), have been described.

Introduction

In 18 multinational countries around the world, 2,130 women infected with the COVID-19 virus were observed, compared to healthy pregnant women. The results showed that newborns born to women diagnosed with COVID-19 had a 23% higher morbidity and mortality rate than babies born to women not diagnosed with COVID-19 (Gunier. RB, 2021). Scientists at the University of Bazer, Switzerland, performed a histological examination of satellite samples of a total of 5 women with COVID-19. Complications with fetal vascular vasculitis and focal thrombosis were found

in 2/5, intervillous fibrin in 4/5, and chorangiosis and malperfusion in 3/5 of women (Mertz K.D. et al., 2021). However, in women with COVID-19, pregnancies often ended in premature birth (32–35 weeks), resulting in 5.3% of underdeveloped lungs in newborns, 2.6% of cerebral hemorrhage, and visual impairment was observed in 3.1% more complications (Menter T., 2020). However, recent studies have shown that histopathological changes in the placenta are also noteworthy. According to the results, fetal and maternal vascular malperfusion was reported in 6.4%,

placental calcification in 5.2%, and chorioamnionitis from placental inflammation in 7% of cases (Chloe A. et al., 2020). However, limited conclusions can be drawn about the effect of COVID-19 infection on placental pathology, as most control groups are absent and most of the studies conducted were observed in the third trimester. Therefore, the study and evaluation of the clinical and morphological status of the fetoplacental complex in pregnant women with COVID-19 is important and will be studied in this study.

There are many unknowns for pregnant women during the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. Clinical experience of pregnancies complicated with infection by other coronaviruses e.g., Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and Middle Eastern Respiratory Syndrome, has led to pregnant woman being considered potentially vulnerable to severe SARS-CoV-2 infection. Physiological changes during pregnancy have a significant impact on the immune system, respiratory system, cardiovascular function, and coagulation. These may have positive or negative effects on COVID-19 disease progression. The impact of SARS-CoV-2 in pregnancy remains to be determined, and a concerted, global effort is required to determine the effects on implantation, fetal growth and development, labor, and neonatal health. Asymptomatic infection presents a further challenge regarding service provision, prevention, and management. Besides the direct impacts of the disease, a plethora of indirect consequences of the pandemic adversely affect maternal health, including reduced access to reproductive health services, increased mental health strain, and increased socioeconomic deprivation.

In this review, we explore the current knowledge of COVID-19 in pregnancy and highlight areas for further research to minimize its impact for women and their children.

BACKGROUND

In December 2019, a cluster of four cases of pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan, China, were reported to the World Health Organization (WHO). Since then, coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) has spread rapidly across the world. On March 12, 2020 the WHO defined the outbreak as a pandemic. Many countries responded by restricting freedom of movement and limiting nonemergency health care to focus resources on COVID-19 care provision. As pregnant women are at greater risk of complications and severe disease from infection with other coronaviruses, including Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and Middle Eastern Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), they were identified as a vulnerable group and were advised to take additional precautions as the COVID-19 pandemic unfolded. To reduce transmission risks for both pregnant women and health care workers, the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) recommended the suspension of much routine antenatal care and replacement with video or telephone consultations whenever possible.

Immunological Response

COVID-19 is a capsulated single-stranded RNA virus. The immunological response to COVID-19, like other viruses, relies on a working immune system. COVID-

19 infection can result in mild disease, in which the virus is cleared effectively by the immune system or severe disease with high mortality rates. The position for pregnant women on this spectrum is unclear. The immune system adapts during pregnancy to allow for the growth of a semiallogenic fetus, resulting in an altered immune response to infections during pregnancy. To understand the COVID-19 phenotype during pregnancy, it is important to understand the pathophysiology and molecular mechanisms of COVID-19 and examine these in the context of the modulated maternal immune response.

SARS-CoV-2, which is transmitted by respiratory droplets, direct contact with fomites, close person-to-person contact and possibly by aerosols generated, enters the body via the nasal passage and infects pulmonary cells via the SARS-CoV receptor angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) and uses transmembrane serine protease 2 (TMPRSS2) for S protein priming. Cells in which ACE-2 and TMPRSS2 are colocalized are likely to be most susceptible to entry by SARS-CoV-2. Infection with SARS-CoV-2 is followed by viral replication and release of the virus, causing pyroptosis [inflammation-mediated programmed cell death occurring in response to a pathological stimulus of the host cell. This releases damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), including ATP and nucleic acids, that trigger an inflammatory response from neighboring cells. This proinflammatory response includes production of IL-6, C-X-C motif chemokine 10 (CXCL10), and type 1 interferons, which act as chemoattractants for monocytes, macrophages, and T cells to the infection

site. This positive feedback loop may lead to excessive inflammation and damage the integrity of the lung, resulting in infection with other (host) microbes. The inflammation caused by SARS-CoV-2 may also result in a "cytokine storm" that can lead to multisystem organ failure. This excessive inflammation is thought to be the cause of severe COVID-19 and is associated with high morbidity and mortality. Among patients with mild symptoms, it is likely that the immune system reacts appropriately to viral infection. The inflammation caused by viral entry attracts T-helper 1 cluster differentiation 4 (Th1 CD4+) T cells that can clear infected cells before further spread and replications of the virus occurs. The virus is blocked further by neutralizing antibodies, and macrophages clear the neutralized viruses and apoptotic cells by phagocytosis.

Study Patients and Control Group Selection

For the COVID-19 group (study group), pregnant women with laboratory-confirmed infection, whose respective placenta specimens have been sent for histologic examination, were eligible for inclusion. This group comprises 19 women who had SARS-CoV-2 infection confirmed either in the second (n = 3) or in the third gestational trimester (n = 16). Initially, we included women who spontaneously sought treatment at Complexo Hospital de Clínicas, Universidade Federal do Paraná (CHC-UFPR) or at Hospital Nossa Senhora das Graças (HNSG), Curitiba, Brazil, for symptoms of COVID-19 varying from mild to severe (n = 9). After the implementation of universal testing for SARS-CoV-2

infection for all obstetrical patients admitted to labor and delivery in both institutions, asymptomatic pregnant women were added thereafter (n=10).

For the Control group (n = 19), placentas of pregnant women who gave birth at CHC-UFPR in years prior to the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak were selected (from 2016 to 2018) and matched in a 1:1 fashion by gestational age at delivery, maternal age, and maternal comorbidities. Historical controls were selected to ensure that women with false-negative test results for SARS-CoV-2 infection were excluded. Gestational age at delivery is a universally used matching variable since there is a correlation between placental development and the advancing gestation, which could interfere in the analysis. Maternal age and maternal comorbidities were also incorporated as matching variables, given their possible role as confounders when analyzing placental abnormalities.

Samples

Submission criteria for placental examination included maternal or fetal conditions previously diagnosed during prenatal care or gross abnormalities noted during delivery, as routinely implemented in both institutions. Therefore, the maternal-positive SARS-CoV-2 testing result was considered an abnormal maternal condition and a placental evaluation criterion.

All placentas were examined according to a standardized protocol that consisted of immediate fixation after delivery in 10 % buffered formalin for 72 h, gross examination with measurement of placental dimensions and chord length, weight evaluation of the placental disc after

trimming of the fetal membranes and umbilical cord, followed by serial sectioning through 1.5-cm interval and cut surface examination. Macroscopic alterations were recorded and sampled. Additional representative samples of the umbilical cord (two sections), the membranes (one fetal membrane roll), and the chorionic plate (at least two full-thickness, non-peripheral sections including maternal and fetal surface) were submitted to paraffin embedding.

Clinical Information

Clinical and laboratory data were obtained from medical records during hospitalization; the mother and the newborn were followed up until discharge from the hospital.

Maternal information sought from each medical record for both groups comprised maternal age and comorbidities, parity, gestational age at delivery, mode of delivery, neonatal birth weight, and APGAR score. All pregnant women in both groups were tested for congenital intrauterine infections (TORCH) during prenatal care; only one (Patient code—PC 20-3744) tested positive for syphilis in the first trimester and received the preconized treatment. For the study group, it was also retrieved the gestational age at and method used for SARS-CoV-2 infection diagnosis, presence or absence of symptoms typically attributed to COVID-19 (body temperature over 38°C, dyspnea, cough, myalgias, nausea and vomiting, diarrhea, headache, anosmia), disease severity (ranging from mild symptoms to critical organ dysfunction), and maternal outcome.

SARS-CoV-2 Testing

Maternal nasopharyngeal swabs specimens (n = 17) were tested for SARS-CoV-2 infection by real-time reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). In the remaining two cases, the diagnosis was achieved by serologic testing (n = 2). Detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in infants was performed in 13 case samples (n = 13), including umbilical cord blood (n = 13), amniotic fluid (n = 3), and infants' nasopharyngeal swabs specimens (n = 6), all of them collected immediately after birth. The mothers' milk was also tested in three cases. Samples from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue were also tested to verify the presence of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in the placenta (n=11). Viral RNA extraction was performed with a commercially available paraffin extraction kit (Qiagen®) in Pelé Pequeno Príncipe Research Institute. SARS-CoV-2 RNA identification tests were performed at CHC-UFPR and HNSG using XGEN MASTER COVID-19 Kit (Mobius Life Science, Inc, Brazil). Quantitative anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgM and IgG dosage was done in peripheral blood samples in both institutions.

Morphologic Analysis

All representative placental samples taken for microscopic assessment underwent routine processing, embedding, sectioning at 5 µm, and staining with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). The qualitative morphological analysis was performed in all placentas from the COVID-19 and Control groups (n = 38) using the Amsterdam Placental Workshop Group Consensus Statement (35). Histological sections containing at least one sample of the umbilical cord, membrane roll, and chorionic plate of every case from both groups were randomly selected and renamed by one research team member

(blinding step). Two experienced perinatal pathologists systematically evaluated the slides.

Selected parameters were computed simply as "present" (yes) or "absent" (no). The extension and intensity of specific alterations were graded following Amsterdam protocol recommendations. The remaining parameters were subdivided into three quantitative categories: <30%, 30% to 70%, and > 70%, to record both the presence and extension of most alterations.

Assessed parameters included features of maternal vascular malperfusion (villous infarction, distal villous hypoplasia, accelerated villous maturation/increase in syncytial knots, decidual acute atherosclerosis, decidual vascular fibrinoid necrosis with or without foam cells, decidual vascular mural hypertrophy, decidual chronic perivasculitis, absence of spiral artery remodeling, decidual arterial thrombosis, persistence of intramural endovascular trophoblast), features of fetal vascular malperfusion (fetal vascular thrombosis, fetal vascular intramural fibrin deposition, avascular villi, stem vessel obliteration/fibromuscular sclerosis, villous stromal-vascular karyorrhexis, vascular ectasia), delayed villous maturation, features of maternal inflammatory response (chorionitis, chorioamnionitis), features of fetal inflammatory response (umbilical vasculitis, funisitis), features of chronic inflammation (chronic deciduous villitis, intervillitis), intervillous thrombi, microcalcification foci, chorangiomas, and membrane meconium and hemosiderin staining.

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